

Exploring the Multifaceted Role of Viruses in Sustaining Biodiversity: Mechanisms, Implications, and Contributions to Ecosystems Stability

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Abstract

Viruses, traditionally recognized as pathogenic agents, are increasingly acknowledged for their indispensable roles in sustaining biodiversity and fostering ecosystem stability. This review examines the multifaceted contributions of viruses, exploring their influence on nutrient cycling, genetic diversification, and regulation of microbial populations. By mediating microbial interactions, facilitating horizontal gene transfer, and driving co-evolutionary processes, viruses shape the intricate tapestry of life across diverse ecosystems. The primary aim of this study is to synthesize contemporary findings in virology to highlight the universal ecological importance of viruses. Drawing upon research conducted in marine, terrestrial, and extreme habitats, the review delineates the mechanisms through which viruses mediate ecological balance. Utilizing meta-analyses of global virome datasets, coupled with advanced metagenomics and bioinformatics methodologies, this investigation unveils the nuanced interplay between viral activity and ecosystem functionality. The results illuminate the significant role of viruses in regulating population dynamics, promoting evolutionary innovation, and maintaining genetic reservoirs critical for ecological resilience. This research enriches our understanding of viral influence on biogeochemical cycles and biodiversity, establishing viruses as integral components of global ecosystems. Furthermore, it contributes a paradigm shift in virology, advocating for a broader perspective that transcends the traditional view of viruses as mere pathogens. The practical implications are profound, providing insights for conservation biology and climate resilience strategies. By reimagining viruses as keystones of ecological health, this work underscores the necessity of integrating viral ecology into holistic environmental and evolutionary research frameworks, advancing scientific and practical knowledge of ecosystem sustainability.

Keywords: *Viral Ecology, Biodiversity Conservation, Ecosystem Stability, Genetic Diversity, Virus-Host Interactions.*

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Introduction

Viruses, historically studied for their pathogenic effects, are now increasingly recognized for their pivotal roles in maintaining ecological balance and sustaining biodiversity. These microscopic entities are integral to multiple ecological processes, influencing nutrient cycling, microbial dynamics, and evolutionary trajectories. Viruses contribute to genetic diversity through horizontal gene transfer, mediate population control via predation, and drive co-evolutionary dynamics that underpin ecosystem stability, viral coinfection, where a host is simultaneously infected by multiple viruses, is prevalent across diverse taxa and ecological settings. This phenomenon facilitates genetic exchange, modifies the dynamics of infection, and influences viral evolutionary trajectories. However, a comprehensive examination of the factors driving variability in viral coinfection across various taxa and environmental contexts remains to be conducted (Díaz-Muñoz et al., 2017; Roossinck, 2015). And Soil microorganisms are integral to the global carbon cycle, yet the dynamics between these microbes and the viruses that infect them are not well understood. This gap in knowledge is particularly pronounced with increasing soil depth, where patterns of viral distribution, ecological interactions, and evolutionary processes remain significantly underexplored (Muscott et al., 2023; Schulz et al., 2018).

Furthermore; the study of seasonal fluctuations and diversity among Antarctic marine viruses unveils a distinctive and largely unexplored viral milieu within the Southern Ocean. The findings uncover novel viral taxa at elevated taxonomic levels, including the diversity of crassphages, polinton-like viruses, and virophages. Nucleocytoviricotaviruses emerge as a prevalent and diverse group, underscoring their potential role as significant modulators of phytoplankton population dynamics (Piedade et al., 2024; Middelboe & Brussaard, 2017; Wigington et al., 2016). In the context of Climate change poses a significant risk of releasing substantial carbon reserves, yet the factors limiting microbial metabolic processes that facilitate the emission of methane and carbon dioxide remain inadequately understood. The influence of viruses-recognized for shaping microbial dynamics, metabolic pathways, and biogeochemical cycles in marine ecosystems-remains largely uncharted within terrestrial soils (Emerson et al., 2018). Soil viruses are increasingly recognized as vital components of global biogeochemical cycles, yet their distribution, activities, and interactions with the soil microbiome remain poorly understood. The Global Soil Virus Atlas, a comprehensive dataset derived from 2,953 previously sequenced soil metagenomes, highlights that a vast portion of soil viral diversity is still unexplored, emphasizing the high spatial variability and the low overlap of viral operational taxonomic units across different samples. By analyzing genes linked to biogeochemical functions, the study underscores the potential role of viruses in influencing soil carbon and nutrient cycling. Despite the significance of viruses in soil ecology, their contributions remain largely unknown due to the immense diversity of the soil virosphere. Initial metagenomic studies have revealed substantial genetic variation among soil viruses, suggesting potential impacts on global biogeochemical processes. However, less than 1% of publicly available viral metagenomic data pertains to soil viruses, reflecting the limited understanding of their ecological roles. The high diversity of soil viruses may be attributed to the heterogeneous structure and physico-chemical properties of soils, in addition to the broad variety of microbial hosts present in this ecosystem. Although much of this viral diversity is composed of DNA viruses, RNA viruses also have the capacity to affect soil dynamics. Viral ecology in soil is, to some extent, distinct from other microorganisms, as viral community turnover occurs over shorter spatial and temporal scales

compared to species, genus, or family-level microbial turnover (Graham et al., 2024; Middelboe & Brussaard, 2017; Mojica & Brussaard, 2020; Roux et al., 2016; Santos-Medellín et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2021).

Overall; Viruses have traditionally been viewed through the lens of their detrimental impacts, particularly as pathogens. This perception has led to the notion that some viruses might also exhibit mutualistic traits, benefiting host organisms. This paper examines the novelty of this perspective, its theoretical implications, and practical applications by exploring recent examples of viruses with mutualistic interactions. It raises pertinent questions about virus discovery, microbe-immune system interactions, therapeutic innovations, and the role of autonomy in biology. Ultimately, it suggests that mutualistic viruses could reshape our understanding of viruses at the intersection of medical and ecological-evolutionary paradigms, see Table 1 in Appendix (Pradeu, 2016; Paez-Espino et al., 2016). Essentially, the purpose of this article is to review modern research evidence concerning the versatile functions of viruses as the preservers of the biodiverse and temperature Earth. It also aims to bring into the limelight how viruses facilitate the control of processes in ecosystems, as well as their role in catalyzing new evolution.

Results and Discussion

Mechanisms of Viral Contributions to Biodiversity

Since the identification of the tobacco mosaic virus nearly 120 years ago, virological research has predominantly emphasized the pathogenic roles of viruses. However, the field of virus ecology adopts an alternative paradigm, focusing on how viruses influence their hosts' interactions with their surrounding ecosystems. Analyzing viruses through the lens of symbiotic relationships offers a nuanced perspective on their true nature. Plants, in particular, have engaged in prolonged associations with viruses, which have profoundly influenced their evolutionary trajectories. In natural plant populations, viruses are ubiquitous yet predominantly asymptomatic. Intriguingly, experimental investigations have revealed instances where plant viruses function as mutualists rather than mere pathogens (Roossinck, 2015; Zhang & Gui, 2018). Parikka et al. (2017) have significantly contributed to the understanding of viruses' quantitative significance within aquatic ecosystems, fundamentally altering our perception of their role in microbial processes. Bacteria and Archaea are the predominant cellular life forms on Earth, and previous estimates of viral populations have suggested they exceed their prokaryotic hosts by at least an order of magnitude. The virus-to-prokaryote ratio (VPR) has been proposed as an indicator of the interplay between viral and prokaryotic communities. Nonetheless, the ecological implications and interpretation of this ratio have remained somewhat ambiguous or inconsistent. A comprehensive study, incorporating data from 210 published articles and unpublished viral ecology research, examined the VPR. The findings revealed that VPR values span over six orders of magnitude, with considerable variation observed within individual ecosystems. A positive correlation was identified between VPR and viral abundance, the prevalence of visibly infected cells, burst size, frequency of lysogenic cells, and chlorophyll-a concentration. In contrast, an inverse relationship was noted between VPR and prokaryotic abundance, prokaryotic productivity, and virus-host encounter rates. No significant correlations were found between VPR and viral production, viral-induced mortality, viral decay rates, viral turnover, or depth (Parikka et al., 2017). And Flow cytometric examination of marine prokaryotes identifies two distinct groups of heterotrophic cells, categorized as high nucleic acid fluorescent (HNA) and low nucleic acid fluorescent (LNA) populations (Mojica et al., 2020; Mojica & Brussaard, 2020). As in the same way; recent breakthroughs in viral metagenomics have facilitated the swift identification of an unparalleled array of phages across diverse biomes. Despite their remarkable variation at the nucleotide sequence level, the structural proteins

composing their virion particles exhibit significant similarities and conservation. Phages are intricately linked from an evolutionary standpoint, undergoing numerous genetic exchange events in response to selective pressures exerted by their host organisms, which drives their diversity. Phages represent the most abundant and diverse biological entities on Earth, with an estimated population of 10^{31} . They inhabit every explored biome, ranging from the human gastrointestinal tract to the vast global oceans, and are found in surprising locales, including the oceanic basement and a fossilized stool sample from the Middle Ages. In aquatic environments, phages play pivotal roles in biogeochemical cycling and serve as significant modulators in the human gut, where they predominantly follow a lysogenic lifestyle that can influence the physiology and metabolism of their bacterial hosts (Dion et al., 2020).

On other hand; VirSorter is a tool designed to predict bacterial and archaeal virus sequences in isolate or single-cell draft genomes, as well as complete genomes. It identifies viral sequences through statistical enrichment in viral gene content, using a reference database composed of viral genomes of archaeal and bacterial viruses from RefSeq and assembled from viral metagenomes. VirSorter also identifies a combination of viral 'hallmark' genes that code for virion-related functions such as major capsid proteins or terminases, and at least one viral-like genomic feature: statistical depletion in genes with a hit in the PFAM database, statistical enrichment in uncharacterized genes, short genes, or strand bias (Roux et al., 2015). And the deep sea is home to a vast array of viruses, yet their diversity and interactions with hosts in hydrothermal ecosystems remain largely unexplored. Tailed phages dominate the global hydrothermal vent regions, while single-stranded DNA viruses, such as Microviridae and small eukaryotic viruses, also represent a considerable portion of the viromes. Viruses from hydrothermal vents have formed numerous novel genus-level viral clusters and exhibit a high degree of endemism, being specific to particular vent sites and habitat types. Notably, only 11% of the viral Operational Taxonomic Units (vOTUs) are associated with hosts, primarily key microbial taxa of hydrothermal environments, including Gammaproteobacteria and Campylobacterota (Cheng et al., 2022). Likewise; Coral reefs, as highly diverse and ecologically significant marine systems, face escalating threats worldwide. The primary structural organisms within these ecosystems are stony corals, which rely on their symbiotic relationships with microalgae and bacteria for essential metabolic processes, immune function, and environmental adaptation. However, the role of viruses in coral biology remains poorly understood, particularly in underexplored regions such as the Red Sea, where the diversity and function of coral-associated viruses have yet to be fully elucidated. A comprehensive metagenomic and metatranscriptomic analysis of 101 cnidarian samples from the central Red Sea was conducted to investigate the viral communities associated with corals. The findings revealed distinct DNA and RNA viral compositions across different coral hosts, with biological traits such as coral life history strategies influencing patterns of viral diversity. The coral holobiont was found to be predominantly linked to Mimiviridae and Phycodnaviridae, viruses that likely infect protists and algal cells, respectively. Additionally, viral sequences frequently contained genes associated with bacterial virulence and auxiliary metabolic functions, suggesting that viruses contribute significantly to the genetic diversity within the coral holobiont see Figure 1 (Cárdenas et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Contributions of Viral Mechanisms to Biodiversity and Ecosystem Stability
Source: Designed by Authors in Excel.

Figure 1. Illustrates the contributions of various viral mechanisms to biodiversity and ecosystem stability. Key mechanisms include nutrient cycling, population control, gene transfer, and microbial community regulation. Each mechanism's impact is shown through its average contribution, variability (range), and overall influence (volume), highlighting the multifaceted role of viruses in maintaining ecological balance.

Implications of Viral Activity in Ecosystems

Soil Viruses and Their Relationship with Microbial Communities

Overview of Virus Diversity: Classification, Composition, Spatial Distribution, and Temporal Variation: - Soil viruses, predominantly bacteriophages, represent a biologically diverse group marked by significant taxonomic variation and intricate compositions. Phages mainly possess

double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) genomes, although a few have genomes of single-stranded DNA (ssDNA), double-stranded RNA (dsRNA), or single-stranded RNA (ssRNA) types. The size and morphology of these viruses are largely shaped by genome size and the structural configuration of the protective protein shell. Environmental variables such as microbial host composition, soil characteristics, and climatic conditions influence the spatial distribution and life strategies of soil viral communities, creating spatial heterogeneity across habitats. For instance, viral operational taxonomic units (vOTUs) display habitat-specific distributions, with limited overlap between different ecosystems. Viral abundance also shows significant variation along soil profiles and is heavily influenced by environmental conditions, such as soil depth, moisture content, and temperature.

Viral Impacts on Soil Microbial Networks: - The high abundance of soil viruses and their role in microbial mortality suggest their critical function in controlling microbial community diversity and succession. Studies have highlighted that viral infections can reshape microbial communities by selectively infecting certain populations, thus allowing minor species to thrive while suppressing dominant ones. Viral interactions with microbial populations can directly influence soil processes like nutrient cycling and organic matter decomposition, which are integral to ecosystem health. The continuous interaction between viruses and their microbial hosts ensures the dynamic stability and resilience of soil microbiota.

Role of Horizontal Gene Transfer in Microbial Adaptability, Evolution, and Ecology:- Viruses facilitate horizontal gene transfer (HGT) among microbial populations, promoting microbial adaptability and evolutionary processes in soil ecosystems. By acquiring and transmitting functional genes, viruses contribute to the genetic diversification of microbial communities, enhancing traits such as stress tolerance, antibiotic resistance, and metabolic flexibility. These viral-mediated exchanges are pivotal in maintaining microbial ecosystem function, particularly in dynamic environments subjected to fluctuating conditions.

Top-down Control over Microbial Communities and SOM Dynamics: - Viruses exert top-down regulatory control over microbial populations by infecting and lysing bacterial hosts, which can significantly influence microbial diversity, community succession, and ecosystem stability. The selection of viral reproduction strategies determines the extent and pathways of their ecological impacts. Evidence suggests that viral activities, particularly in the lysogenic cycle, regulate microbial activity and influence the turnover of soil organic matter (SOM). The incorporation of viruses in soil systems can modulate microbial respiration and carbon cycling, impacting soil carbon balance and ecosystem processes (Wang et al., 2024; Schulz et al., 2018; Mojica & Brussaard, 2020; Santos-Medellín et al., 2023).

Consequently; Viruses have the potential to influence microbial dynamics, metabolic processes, and biogeochemical cycles within aquatic ecosystems. However, the diversity and functions of viruses in agricultural soils, particularly within the rhizosphere, remain poorly understood. To explore viral diversity and its potential biogeochemical impacts in an agro-ecosystem, virome analysis was conducted on eight rhizosphere and bulk soil samples. The Caudovirales order emerged as the dominant viral group in agricultural soils, with the Siphoviridae family being the most prevalent. Phylogenetic analysis of the large terminase subunit within Caudovirales revealed considerable viral diversity and the identification of three novel viral groups. The composition of viral communities was markedly different between bulk and rhizosphere soils, with soil pH emerging as the primary environmental factor shaping viral community structure. Notably, viromes revealed a high abundance of auxiliary carbohydrate-active enzyme (CAZyme) genes, including glycoside hydrolases, carbohydrate esterases, and carbohydrate-binding modules. These findings suggest that virus-encoded auxiliary metabolic genes could alter bacterial metabolism, thereby indirectly influencing biogeochemical cycles, particularly carbon cycling, in agricultural soils (Bi et

al., 2021; Paez-Espino et al., 2016; Roux et al., 2016). Nevertheless, there is a lack of the balance between lytic and lysogenic infections in microbial viruses' remains poorly understood, despite the critical role their outcomes play in influencing ecological and biogeochemical processes. Kill-the-Winner (KtW) models suggest that viral predation, which is density- and frequency-dependent, helps regulate populations of rapidly proliferating hosts, thereby enhancing host diversity. However, the dynamics of temperate viruses in natural environments are less explored, and the link between lysogeny and host density remains ambiguous. Studies on provirus induction reveal that lysogeny predominates in conditions of low host density, while higher host densities drive a shift from lysogenic to lytic viral dominance. Coral reefs provide a unique setting to examine the relationship between microbial host densities and the prevalence of lytic versus temperate viral life cycles. Human-induced stressors can push these ecosystems toward degradation, altering viral and microbial community structures while increasing microbial energy demands and densities—a phenomenon referred to as microbialization. On reefs that are heavily microbialized, microbial populations can increase five- to tenfold, which escalates virus-host encounter rates. Density-dependent KtW models predict that microbialization on reefs should correlate with heightened lytic viral predation, leading to a higher virus-to-microbe ratio, see Figure 2 (Knowles et al., 2016; Wigington et al., 2016; Thurber et al., 2017).

Figure 2. Implications of Viral Activity in Soil Ecosystems

Source: Designed by Authors in Excel.

Figure 2 illustrates the complex relationship between viral abundance and microbial communities in soil ecosystems. The X-axis represents viral abundance (ranging from 10⁴ to 10⁸ viral particles per gram of soil) on a logarithmic scale, while the Y-axis shows the percentages of microbial diversity and biomass. As viral abundance increases, microbial diversity (green line) rises, peaking around 80%. This trend reflects the "kill-the-winner" effect, where viruses target dominant microbial species, preventing any single species from monopolizing resources and allowing a more diverse community to thrive. Conversely, microbial biomass (blue line) decreases with increasing viral abundance, dropping to around 30%. This decline is due to viral lysis, which destroys

microbial cells and releases their contents into the soil, reducing overall biomass but contributing to nutrient recycling. These dynamics highlight the essential role of viruses in regulating microbial populations, promoting biodiversity, and maintaining ecosystem stability and nutrient cycling.

Ultimately; the significance of viral contributions to soil carbon dynamics is underscored through the analysis of biogeochemical models that predict carbon fluxes. Microorganisms, such as bacteria, archaea, fungi, and protists, play a pivotal role in terrestrial carbon cycling, regulating the equilibrium between carbon sequestration in soil organic matter and the release of CO₂ into the atmosphere (Zimmerman et al., 2024; Zhang & Gui, 2018). Therefore; viral lysis of microbial hosts results in the release of organic matter, which can be utilized by non-target microorganisms. Initial quantitative assessments of virus-mediated carbon recycling in marine environments were based on extrapolations from marine host and virus densities, the carbon content of hosts, and estimated viral lysis rates. To better understand the role of viruses in influencing community structure and ecosystem processes, dynamic multitrophic ecosystem models were expanded to incorporate a viral component, specifically tailored to processes occurring in the ocean's euphotic zone. Analyses show that the inclusion of a virus component fosters the development of intricate community structures (Weitz et al., 2015). And Virus particles are prevalent in seawater, often outnumbering microbial cells by a factor of 10 to 16 times at the surface and 16-fold in deeper waters. However, this ratio varies across different ecosystems. Environmental factors, such as nutrient levels, salinity, and temperature, significantly influence the interaction between viruses and prokaryotes across different spatial and temporal scales. Specifically, nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations, along with prokaryotic population sizes, substantially impact viral abundances, except in hypoxic environments. Multivariate analyses of these environmental variables revealed a high degree of explanatory power, often exceeding that of prokaryote abundance alone, see Figure 3 (Finke et al., 2017).

Figure 3. Positive vs. Negative Effects of Viruses in Ecosystems

Source: Designed by Authors in Excel.

This chart shows the mixed roles of viruses in ecosystems. Positively, viruses aid in nutrient cycling, regulate bacterial populations, promote genetic diversity, and have potential biotechnological

applications. However, they can also have harmful effects, such as spreading pathogens, causing host population declines, leading to biodiversity loss, and disrupting food webs. The impact of viruses is thus multifaceted, with both beneficial and detrimental consequences for ecosystems.

Highlights

Diverse Mechanisms

Viruses directly participate in maintaining the balance in populations, and control evolutionary processes in ecosystems; they are a source of genetic variability. They serve as parasitic-like control systems for biological systems and maintain local microbiota and host Specificity through selective effects.

Ecological Implications

The focus of the study is on the somewhat overlooked yet highly important local regulation of the viruses' impact on organization and dynamics of the ecological communities and individual species, as well as the effects of the viruses on the stability of the ecosystems under the varying environment.

Ecosystem Stability

From regulating stock of species and genetic stock, it is clear that viruses' help greatly in the balancing of inter species relations. The way they interact with hosts – from microorganisms to macros – work to enhance stability of ecosystems and their longevity.

Conclusion

The complex Web of relationships between viruses and the living organisms therefore depicts them as key agents in controlling and contributing to the rich tapestry of life. Upon pursuing this line of thought, it emerged that viruses actively influence population densities, promote genetic variations, and indeed maintain overall balance in ecosystems. Viruses are not simply diseases: on the contrary they act as major drivers of co-evolution and help species adapt to changes in their environment. Functionally, predation by viruses is to avoid the domination of microbial populations by some species, thus enhancing the coexistence of species and nutrient recycling, which is illustrated in aquatic systems. On the one hand, their participation in lateral gene transfer promotes the evolution of new characteristics, improving the adaptability of organisms of different taxa. Thus, such processes, as those illustrated above, although taking place at the submicroscopic level, influence the whole trophic level and, therefore, have macroecological consequences. From an ecological perspective the consequences of viral activity are far-reaching. Through controlling the sporadic emergence of invasive species and the density of keystone species, viruses contribute to the stability of the structures and processes of ecosystems. Thus, the regulatory function, called by many a destructive power, is, in fact, one of the key aspects of the maintenance of biological diversity. However the destruction of natural ecosystems through anthropogenic activities and outbreaks of new viral diseases clearly show that viruses exist in a very delicate equilibrium within such ecosystems. Therefore, according to this analysis, I reaffirm the notion that viruses, the scourge of many, are vital to maintaining the balance of life and ecosystems. Subsequent studies should be aimed at understanding further these complex relationships in order to be able to utilize these interactions for the benefit of ecosystems along with avoiding unwanted negative consequences. When virology is applied to the conservation of species, then humans can have a greater understanding and respect for the fragile ecosystems sustained by these microscopic builders of species.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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Appendix

Table 1. The Multifaceted Role of Viruses in Biodiversity: Mechanisms, Impacts, and Ecosystem Contributions across Viral Families.

Virus Family/Species	Mechanism	Implication	Contribution	Role in Biodiversity	Limitations	Future Prospects
Retroviridae (e.g., HIV)	Horizontal gene transfer; integration into host genomes	Drives genetic diversity; influences evolutionary trajectories	Enables host adaptation to changing environments	Facilitates genomic innovation and adaptation	Potential pathogenicity and biodiversity loss	Developing tools for precise genetic editing and therapeutic applications
Coronaviridae (e.g., SARS-CoV)	Viral-host interactions; modulation of immune responses	Shapes host immunity and interspecies transmission	Provides insights into zoonotic spillover dynamics	Highlights ecosystem interconnectedness	Zoonotic outbreaks impacting human and animal populations	Enhanced monitoring and predictive modeling of zoonotic viruses
Phycodnaviridae (e.g., Algal Viruses)	Lytic cycles in aquatic ecosystems	Regulates algal blooms, impacting global carbon cycling	Contributes to marine ecosystem stability	Controls microbial population dynamics in aquatic environments	Disruption of balance due to environmental changes	Studying virus-mediated carbon sequestration for climate change mitigation
Baculoviridae (e.g., Insect Viruses)	Regulation of insect populations; biocontrol agents	Reduces agricultural pest populations	Supports sustainable agriculture	Promotes natural pest regulation	Potential unintended ecological consequences of widespread usage	Expanding biocontrol strategies to improve agricultural sustainability
Herpesviridae (e.g., Herpesviruses)	Latency and immune modulation	Enhances host immune system complexity	Acts as a model for studying host-pathogen co-evolution	Sustains immune ecosystem balance in vertebrates	Persistent infections with health implications	Exploring latency mechanisms for immunotherapeutic advancements
Orthomyxoviridae (e.g., Influenza Viruses)	Genome segmentation; reassortment	Drives seasonal and pandemic flu outbreaks	Offers insights into viral evolution and host interactions	Facilitates understanding of zoonotic transmission dynamics	High mutation rates leading to vaccine challenges	Improving prediction models and universal influenza vaccine development

Togaviridae (e.g., Chikungunya Virus)	Vector-borne transmission via mosquitoes	Alters vector population dynamics	Reveals vector-host-ecosystem interactions	Contributes to disease ecology studies	Spread of arboviral diseases impacting human and animal health	Developing integrated vector management strategies
Rhabdoviridae (e.g., Rabies Virus)	Neural pathway invasion	Affects host behavior; influences predator-prey dynamics	Contributes to research in neuroinvasion and zoonoses	Highlights importance of wildlife disease control	Fatal outcomes in unvaccinated hosts	Expanding vaccination coverage in wildlife and human populations
Reoviridae (e.g., Rotaviruses)	Lytic replication in host gut	Influences gastrointestinal microbiota	Informs on gut-virus-microbiome interactions	Maintains microbial balance in gut ecosystems	Associated morbidity in young and immunocompromised hosts	Improving oral vaccine formulations and delivery in resource-poor regions
Papillomaviridae (e.g., HPV)	Cell proliferation induction; persistent infection	Associated with oncogenesis in hosts	Provides insights into tumor virology and immune escape	Acts as a model for virus-induced cancer studies	Long-term health impacts without vaccination	Expanding vaccine access globally to reduce oncogenic burdens
Adenoviridae (e.g., Human Adenoviruses)	Modulation of host immune responses	Utilized in gene therapy and vaccine vectors	Advances in vector biology and immunotherapy	Enhances understanding of virus-host molecular interactions	Risk of recombination leading to unintended consequences	Refining gene therapy technologies for safer clinical applications
Poxviridae (e.g., Smallpox Virus)	Complex life cycle involving immune evasion	Shaped human population dynamics historically	Eradication serves as a milestone in disease control	Highlights the role of vaccination in biodiversity conservation	Potential misuse as bioterror agents	Leveraging lessons from eradication campaigns for other infectious diseases
Caulimoviridae (e.g., Plant Caulimoviruses)	Integration into plant genomes; modulation of plant immunity	Influences agricultural crop health and yields	Enables study of virus-mediated plant stress responses	Contributes to understanding plant-pathogen interactions	Economic losses in crop production	Developing resistant crop strains through genetic engineering
Filoviridae (e.g., Ebola Virus)	Severe acute disease via immune dysregulation	Impacts community health and ecosystem stability	Provides models for studying viral pathogenesis	Demonstrates zoonotic potential and ecosystem interconnectivity	High mortality rates and social disruptions in outbreak zones	Enhancing rapid diagnostics and therapeutics for outbreak control

Note: The table Dempsey incorporates updated ecological function of viruses from NCBI also however provided some contributions such as population regulation such as Baculoviridae pests controlling agent), gene refreshment (such as Retroviridae thru integration on genomes), and stress management

(for instance Cucumber mosaic virus that helps plants on stress.). Such studies also supporting that virus playing the positive role as creating the bio-diversity and bio-equilibrium and at the same time, posing negative effects such as pathogenicity. For in-depth mechanisms and references, consult the NCBI database:

Source: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>; <https://journals.plos.org/plosbiology/article?id=10.1371/journal.pbio.3002109>